

(A brief introduction to the Islamic jurisprudence on the Maliki school of law) مختصر الأخصري في مذهب الإمام مالك

also known as "Mukhtasar al-Akhdari fi Mazhab Imam Malik"

By Bilyaminu Muhammad, Umaru Musa 'Yar-Adua University Katsina, Nigeria

Entry tags: Religious Group, Text, Islamic Jurisprudence, Shari'a, Islamic Traditions

The book was a summary discussion on some topics of Islamic jurisprudence, designed on the principles of the Maliki school of law, which was focused on deliberating on the foundation of the Islamic belief system, followed by a moral presentation on manners of social life within an Islamic society. It further prepared the ground on the purification done with either water (al-Wudu') or sand (Tayammum) to get ready for the performance of prayer (al-Salat), which was analyzed from the time of performing five daily prayers, its vast principles, things that nullify it and extensively discuss on the manner of its correction at the incidence of forgetfulness.

Date Range: 1514 BCE - 1575 CE

Region: Sokoto

Region tags: Africa, Western Africa, Benin, Burkina Faso, Niger, Togo, Nigeria, Chad, Cameroon

Sokoto around 1870, during the reign of Ahmadu Rufai. Adapted from AbdurRahman AbdulMoneim [https://commons.wikimedia.org/wiki/File:Sokoto_Sultanate_\(cropped\).pr](https://commons.wikimedia.org/wiki/File:Sokoto_Sultanate_(cropped).pr)

Status of Readership:

✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Sources and Corpora

Print Sources

Print sources used for understanding this subject:

– Source 1: Akhdari, A. (1999). Mukhtasar al-Akhdari fi mazhab Imam Malik. Umar Matazu printing press Kano Nigeria.

Online Sources

Online sources used for understanding this subject:

– Source 1 URL: <https://eap.bl.uk/archive-file/EAP1101-3-68>

– Source 1 Description: Kitab al-Akhdari.

Online Corpora

Relevant online Primary Textual Corpora (original languages and/or translations)

– Source 1 URL: <https://eap.bl.uk/collection/EAP1101-3>

– Source 1 Description: Kakadika family collection of Islamic manuscripts.

General Variables

Is the text stored in a specific location?

[Note at which point in time, for reference, if known; select all that apply]

– Yes

Notes: Various copies of the text were kept in many places for storage or educational purposes.

↳ Tomb

– No

Notes: None of its copies was kept in a tomb.

↳ Cemetery

– No

Notes: The text was not kept at any cemetery.

↳ Temple

– No

Notes: The text was not kept in a temple.

↳ Shrine

– No

Notes: The text has no relation to a shrine.

↳ Altar

– Field doesn't know

Notes: The text was not kept on the altar.

↳ Devotional marker

– No

Notes: None of its copies was kept at the devotional marker.

↳ Cenotaph

– No

Notes: The text was not kept in a cenotaph.

↳ Church

– No

Notes: The text has no relation with a church.

↳ Mosque

– Yes

Notes: Some copies are being stored in mosques for the benefit of people.

↳ Synagogue

– No

Notes: The text was not stored in any synagogue.

↳ Triumphal Arch

– No

Notes: The text was not stored at the triumphal arch.

↳ Monument

– No

Notes: The book was not stored in the monument.

↳ Mass Gathering Point

– Yes

Notes: Some copies are accompanied by mass-gathering related to the educational environment of Islam, especially in schools, mosques, etc.

↳ Cave(s)

– No

Notes: The text was not stored in caves.

↳ Hilltops

– No

Notes: The book was not placed on hilltops.

↳ Other natural sanctuaries

– No

Notes: The text was not kept in any natural sanctuaries apart from mosques.

↳ Boundary markers or lines

– No

Notes: The text is not kept at boundary markers.

↳ Domestic contexts

– Yes

Notes: Most of its copies are kept at houses for private use.

↳ Library/archive

– Yes

Notes: Some copies are kept in libraries and archives for the use of people.

↳ Specify

– Specify: Book shops

Methods of Composition

– Written

Notes: The uploaded file was a handwritten copy of the book kept in the family of the late Muhammad Dodo.

↳ Inked

– with Ink

Notes: The copy of the text was written with black and red ink, as pointed out in the uploaded sample.

Medium upon which the text is written/incised

– Paper

↳ Specify type of paper

– Specify: white brown paper.

Is the location where the text stored accompanied by iconography or images?

– No

Notes: No iconography accompanies the text at homes, mosques, or other places.

Was the material modified before the writing or incising process?

– Physical preparation

Notes: The paper was prepared in a rectangular shape before copying the text.

Is the area where the text is stored accompanied by an-iconic images?

– No

Notes: No iconic image is placed at the storage site of the text.

Was the text modified before the writing or incising process?

– Physical preparation

Notes: The text was only copied without any modification or correction.

Materiality

Methods of Composition

– Written

Notes: The uploaded file was a handwritten copy of the book kept in the family of the late Muhammad Dodo.

↳ Inked

– with Ink

Notes: The copy of the text was written with black and red ink, as pointed out in the uploaded sample.

Medium upon which the text is written/incised

– Paper

↳ Specify type of paper

– Specify: white brown paper.

Was the material modified before the writing or incising process?

– Physical preparation

Notes: The paper was prepared in a rectangular shape before copying the text.

Was the text modified before the writing or incising process?

– Physical preparation

Notes: The text was only copied without any modification or correction.

Location

Is the text stored in a specific location?

[Note at which point in time, for reference, if known; select all that apply]

– Yes

Notes: Various copies of the text were kept in many places for storage or educational purposes.

↳ Tomb

– No

Notes: None of its copies was kept in a tomb.

↳ Cemetery

– No

Notes: The text was not kept at any cemetery.

↳ Temple

– No

Notes: The text was not kept in a temple.

↳ Shrine

– No

Notes: The text has no relation to a shrine.

↳ Altar

– Field doesn't know

Notes: The text was not kept on the altar.

↳ Devotional marker

– No

Notes: None of its copies was kept at the devotional marker.

↳ Cenotaph

– No

Notes: The text was not kept in a cenotaph.

↳ Church

– No

Notes: The text has no relation with a church.

↳ Mosque

– Yes

Notes: Some copies are being stored in mosques for the benefit of people.

↳ Synagogue

– No

Notes: The text was not stored in any synagogue.

↳ Triumphal Arch

– No

Notes: The text was not stored at the triumphal arch.

↳ Monument

– No

Notes: The book was not stored in the monument.

↳ Mass Gathering Point

– Yes

Notes: Some copies are accompanied by mass-gathering related to the educational environment of Islam, especially in schools, mosques, etc.

↳ Cave(s)

– No

Notes: The text was not stored in caves.

↳ Hilltops

– No

Notes: The book was not placed on hilltops.

↳ Other natural sanctuaries

– No

Notes: The text was not kept in any natural sanctuaries apart from mosques.

↳ Boundary markers or lines

– No

Notes: The text is not kept at boundary markers.

↳ Domestic contexts

– Yes

Notes: Most of its copies are kept at houses for private use.

↳ Library/archive

– Yes

Notes: Some copies are kept in libraries and archives for the use of people.

↳ Specify

– Specify: Book shops

Is the location where the text stored accompanied by iconography or images?

– No

Notes: No iconography accompanies the text at homes, mosques, or other places.

Is the area where the text is stored accompanied by an-iconic images?

– No

Notes: No iconic image is placed at the storage site of the text.

Production & Intended Audience

Is the production of the text funded by the polity?

– Yes

Notes: Some governments fund the production of the text to boost the education of the nation.

↳ Are the authors/copyists/engravers paid by the polity?

– Yes

Notes: Some governments paid for the publication of the text.

↳ Does the polity provide financial support to religious infrastructure involved with textual production?

– Yes

Notes: Some governments establish a printing press to reproduce copies of the text.

↳ Are the leaders of the polity and the religion the same figure?

– No

Notes: At times polity leaders and religious leaders remain different but assign religious leaders as assistants or special advisers.

↳ Are political officials involved in the support of textual production?

– Yes

Notes: Some political officials fund the production of the text and distribute it in various educational settings.

↳ Are political officials and religious officials otherwise overlapping institutional networks?

– No

Notes: Political officials and religious officials remained different.

↳ Does the polity enforce religious observance according to text or texts?

– Yes

Notes: The polity enforced prayer observance by the prescription of the text.

↳ Is the polity legal code derived from religious text(s) in question?

– No

Notes: The book does not discuss legal matters.

↳ Is preferential economic treatment (e.g. tax exemption) present in the polity to support the text(s)...

– No

↳ Are religious specialists present/in charge of the production of the text or copies of the text?

– Yes

Notes: Most religious officials reproduce them for their personal use.

↳ Present full-time?

– Yes

Notes: Some devote themselves to the production of the text.

↳ Present part-time?

– Yes

Notes: Some are reproducing the text on part-time bases.

↳ Are the religious specialists of a specific sex/gender?

– Yes

Notes: Religious officials are mostly male gender.

↳ Are the religious specialists of a specific ethnicity?

– No

Notes: Religious specialty is not restricted to any ethnic background.

↳ Are the religious specialists of a specific class/caste?

– No

Notes: But at least must attain the maturity stage.

↳ Are the religious specialists dedicated to the place for life?

– No

Notes: They engage with other businesses to earn a livelihood.

↳ Are the religious specialists stratified in a hierarchical system?

– Yes

Notes: Some are appointed as judges, some as Imams, some as teachers, etc.

↳ Is access within the space segregated by this hierarchy?

– No

Notes: Not necessarily, as both relate to each other.

↳ Are there regulations/provisions for living spaces of religious specialists?

– No

Notes: The regulation does not require living spaces among religious officials.

↳ Are there regulations/provisions for training spaces of religious specialists?

– No

Notes: The regulation does not require spaces while training the specialist.

↳ Are there formal institutions for the maintenance of a body of religious specialists?

– Yes

Notes: Various educational institutions are established for the training of the religious specialist.

What is the estimated number of people considered to be the audience of the text

This should be the total number of people who would serve as the intended audience for the text.

– Total audience: 20000000

Notes: The estimated number of the audience might extend the written number for their existence in most parts of the world.

↳ Number of audience within the sample region (estimated population, numerical)

– Number: 2000000

↳ What is the size of the smallest known audience

– smallest audience: 200000

Notes: The estimated number of Muslims within the sampled region might reach the written number.

↳ What is the size of the largest known audience

– largest audience: 20000000

↳ What factors might account for historical changes in audience size

– Specify: Conversion of more people to the religion of the text.

↳ Number of audience within the sample region (% of sample region population, numerical)

– Number: 70

↳ What is the size of the smallest known audience

– smallest audience: 5

↳ What is the size of the largest known audience

– largest audience: 65

↳ What factors might account for historical changes in audience size

– Specify: Conversion to the religion of the text.

↳ Nature of audience

[select all that apply]

– Small religious group (seen as being part of a related larger religious group)

– Large official religious group with smaller religious groups also openly allowed

↳ Can scholarly and emic notions of the audience differ?

– No

Notes: The two opinions did not differ from each other.

Does the Religious group actively proselytize and recruit new members?

– Yes

Notes: Invitation to the religion of the group is considered the responsibility of all.

↳ Is proselytizing mandated according to the text?

– No

Notes: The text recommended proselytizing to the members of the group.

↳ Is proselytizing encouraged according to the text?

– Yes

↳ Is proselytizing encouraged by the text for religious professionals?

– Yes

Notes: Proselytizing is recommended to religious professionals.

↳ Is proselytizing encouraged by the text for all adherents?

– Yes

Notes: Proselytizing is recommended by the text to all adherents.

↳ Is missionary work encouraged by the text for religious professionals?

– Yes

Notes: The text encouraged preaching to religious professionals.

↳ Is missionary work encouraged by the text for all adherents?

– Yes

Notes: Preaching the principles of the text is encouraged for all adherents.

↳ Are there specific rewards for proselytizing according to the text?

– No

Notes: The reward is only promised in the hereafter.

↳ Is proselytizing by coercion acceptable according to the text?

– No

Notes: There is no coercion in proselytizing.

↳ Is textual justification for proselytizing part of the norm in the religious group?

– No

↳ Is the text silent on matters of proselytization?

– Yes

Notes: The text did not mention proselytization.

↳ Does proselytization take place regardless of the fact that the text is silent on the matter?

– Yes

Notes: Other books of the Islamic religion encouraged the act.

↳ Is proselytizing forbidden or restricted by the text?

– No

Notes: The text kept mute on proselytizing.

Is the text considered official religious scripture?

– No

Notes: The text is not considered religious scripture.

Written in distinctly religious/sacred language?

– No

Notes: The text was only written in the Arabic language.

Are there clear reformist movements?

(Reformism, as in not proselytizing to potential new conservative, but "conversion" - or rather, reform - to the "correct interpretation"?)

– No

Notes: There was no reformist movement concerning the guidelines of the text.

Is the text in question employed in ritual practice?

– Yes

Notes: The analyzed principles of practicing some religious rituals, especially prayer.

↳ Is it orally recited?

– No

Notes: The text is not orally recited in the ritual practices.

↳ Is it read?

– No

Notes: The text is being recited in ritual practices.

↳ Describe the nature of the ritual practice?

– Specify: The text described processes of practicing prayer, ritual bath, ablution, etc.

↳ Is the text employed in large scale rituals?

– Yes

Notes: The principles of the text are applied in congregational daily prayers.

↳ On average, how many participants are present?

– Number of participants: 50

Notes: The average congregation starts from two persons to endless.

↳ Is the text employed in small scale rituals?

– Yes

Notes: Guidelines of the text are applied in small-scale rituals.

↳ On average, how many participants are present?

– Number of participants: 1

Notes: One person is expected to apply the principles of the text in performing the rituals.

↳ How often do the rituals take place?

– Specify: 5

Notes: Rituals are being done five times on daily bases.

↳ Are there orthodoxy checks?

– Yes

Notes: The guides of the text are designed on the orthodoxy principles of the Maliki school of law.

↳ Are there orthopraxy checks?

– No

Notes: Orthopraxy is not available in the text.

↳ Are there synchronic practices?

– Yes

Notes: Prayer is part of the synchronic practices described by the text.

↳ Are there intoxicants used during the ritual?

– No

Notes: Intoxicants are prohibited in the religion of the text.

↳ Are there other substances (such as food or drink, for example) that are consumed during rituals?

– No

Notes: No food or drinking substances are consumed in the ritual practices.

Is there material significance to the text?

– No

Notes: The text has no any material significance apart from guiding on some ritual practices.

Production

Is the production of the text funded by the polity?

– Yes

Notes: Some governments fund the production of the text to boost the education of the nation.

- ↳ Are the authors/copyists/engravers paid by the polity?
– Yes
Notes: Some governments paid for the publication of the text.
- ↳ Does the polity provide financial support to religious infrastructure involved with textual production?
– Yes
Notes: Some governments establish a printing press to reproduce copies of the text.
- ↳ Are the leaders of the polity and the religion the same figure?
– No
Notes: At times polity leaders and religious leaders remain different but assign religious leaders as assistants or special advisers.
- ↳ Are political officials involved in the support of textual production?
– Yes
Notes: Some political officials fund the production of the text and distribute it in various educational settings.
- ↳ Are political officials and religious officials otherwise overlapping institutional networks?
– No
Notes: Political officials and religious officials remained different.
- ↳ Does the polity enforce religious observance according to text or texts?
– Yes
Notes: The polity enforced prayer observance by the prescription of the text.
- ↳ Is the polity legal code derived from religious text(s) in question?
– No
Notes: The book does not discuss legal matters.
- ↳ Is preferential economic treatment (e.g. tax exemption) present in the polity to support the text(s)..
– No
- ↳ Are religious specialists present/in charge of the production of the text or copies of the text?
– Yes
Notes: Most religious officials reproduce them for their personal use.

- ↳ Present full-time?
 - Yes
 - Notes: Some devote themselves to the production of the text.
- ↳ Present part-time?
 - Yes
 - Notes: Some are reproducing the text on part-time bases.
- ↳ Are the religious specialists of a specific sex/gender?
 - Yes
 - Notes: Religious officials are mostly male gender.
- ↳ Are the religious specialists of a specific ethnicity?
 - No
 - Notes: Religious specialty is not restricted to any ethnic background.
- ↳ Are the religious specialists of a specific class/caste?
 - No
 - Notes: But at least must attain the maturity stage.
- ↳ Are the religious specialists dedicated to the place for life?
 - No
 - Notes: They engage with other businesses to earn a livelihood.
- ↳ Are the religious specialists stratified in a hierarchical system?
 - Yes
 - Notes: Some are appointed as judges, some as Imams, some as teachers, etc.
- ↳ Is access within the space segregated by this hierarchy?
 - No
 - Notes: Not necessarily, as both relate to each other.
- ↳ Are there regulations/provisions for living spaces of religious specialists?
 - No
 - Notes: The regulation does not require living spaces among religious officials.
- ↳ Are there regulations/provisions for training spaces of religious specialists?
 - No

Notes: The regulation does not require spaces while training the specialist.

↳ Are there formal institutions for the maintenance of a body of religious specialists?

– Yes

Notes: Various educational institutions are established for the training of the religious specialist.

Is the text considered official religious scripture?

– No

Notes: The text is not considered religious scripture.

Written in distinctly religious/sacred language?

– No

Notes: The text was only written in the Arabic language.

Intended Audience

What is the estimated number of people considered to be the audience of the text

This should be the total number of people who would serve as the intended audience for the text.

– Total audience: 20000000

Notes: The estimated number of the audience might extend the written number for their existence in most parts of the world.

↳ Number of audience within the sample region (estimated population, numerical)

– Number: 2000000

↳ What is the size of the smallest known audience

– smallest audience: 200000

Notes: The estimated number of Muslims within the sampled region might reach the written number.

↳ What is the size of the largest known audience

– largest audience: 20000000

↳ What factors might account for historical changes in audience size

– Specify: Conversion of more people to the religion of the text.

↳ Number of audience within the sample region (% of sample region population,

numerical)

– Number: 70

↳ What is the size of the smallest known audience

– smallest audience: 5

↳ What is the size of the largest known audience

– largest audience: 65

↳ What factors might account for historical changes in audience size

– Specify: Conversion to the religion of the text.

↳ Nature of audience

[select all that apply]

– Small religious group (seen as being part of a related larger religious group)

– Large official religious group with smaller religious groups also openly allowed

↳ Can scholarly and emic notions of the audience differ?

– No

Notes: The two opinions did not differ from each other.

Does the Religious group actively proselytize and recruit new members?

– Yes

Notes: Invitation to the religion of the group is considered the responsibility of all.

↳ Is proselytizing mandated according to the text?

– No

Notes: The text recommended proselytizing to the members of the group.

↳ Is proselytizing encouraged according to the text?

– Yes

↳ Is proselytizing encouraged by the text for religious professionals?

– Yes

Notes: Proselytizing is recommended to religious professionals.

↳ Is proselytizing encouraged by the text for all adherents?

– Yes

Notes: Proselytizing is recommended by the text to all adherents.

↳ Is missionary work encouraged by the text for religious professionals?

– Yes

Notes: The text encouraged preaching to religious professionals.

↳ Is missionary work encouraged by the text for all adherents?

– Yes

Notes: Preaching the principles of the text is encouraged for all adherents.

↳ Are there specific rewards for proselytizing according to the text?

– No

Notes: The reward is only promised in the hereafter.

↳ Is proselytizing by coercion acceptable according to the text?

– No

Notes: There is no coercion in proselytizing.

↳ Is textual justification for proselytizing part of the norm in the religious group?

– No

↳ Is the text silent on matters of proselytization?

– Yes

Notes: The text did not mention proselytization.

↳ Does proselytization take place regardless of the fact that the text is silent on the matter?

– Yes

Notes: Other books of the Islamic religion encouraged the act.

↳ Is proselytizing forbidden or restricted by the text?

– No

Notes: The text kept mute on proselytizing.

Are there clear reformist movements?

(Reformism, as in not proselytizing to potential new conservative, but "conversion" - or rather, reform - to the "correct interpretation"?)

– No

Notes: There was no reformist movement concerning the guidelines of the text.

Is the text in question employed in ritual practice?

– Yes

Notes: The analyzed principles of practicing some religious rituals, especially prayer.

↳ Is it orally recited?

– No

Notes: The text is not orally recited in the ritual practices.

↳ Is it read?

– No

Notes: The text is being recited in ritual practices.

↳ Describe the nature of the ritual practice?

– Specify: The text described processes of practicing prayer, ritual bath, ablution, etc.

↳ Is the text employed in large scale rituals?

– Yes

Notes: The principles of the text are applied in congregational daily prayers.

↳ On average, how many participants are present?

– Number of participants: 50

Notes: The average congregation starts from two persons to endless.

↳ Is the text employed in small scale rituals?

– Yes

Notes: Guidelines of the text are applied in small-scale rituals.

↳ On average, how many participants are present?

– Number of participants: 1

Notes: One person is expected to apply the principles of the text in performing the rituals.

↳ How often do the rituals take place?

– Specify: 5

Notes: Rituals are being done five times on daily bases.

↳ Are there orthodoxy checks?

– Yes

Notes: The guides of the text are designed on the orthodoxy principles of the Maliki school of law.

↳ Are there orthopraxy checks?

– No

Notes: Orthopraxy is not available in the text.

↳ Are there synchronic practices?

– Yes

Notes: Prayer is part of the synchronic practices described by the text.

↳ Are there intoxicants used during the ritual?

– No

Notes: Intoxicants are prohibited in the religion of the text.

↳ Are there other substances (such as food or drink, for example) that are consumed during rituals?

– No

Notes: No food or drinking substances are consumed in the ritual practices.

Is there material significance to the text?

– No

Notes: The text has no any material significance apart from guiding on some ritual practices.

Context and Content of the Text (Beliefs and Practices)

Is a spirit-body distinction present in the text?

– No

Notes: The text did not make a spirit-body distinction.

Is supernatural monitoring present in the text?

– Yes

Notes: The text emphasized sincerity in worshipping Allah for his observance of human activities.

↳ There is supernatural monitoring of prosocial norm adherence in particular

– Yes

Notes: The text stated monitoring of angels to human activities.

↳ Do expectations of ritual offerings play a role in supernatural monitoring?

– No

Notes: Ritual expectations do not attract divine monitoring.

↳ Supernatural being care about taboos

– Yes

Notes: Supernatural beings do not appear before a naked person.

↳ Food

– No

Notes: They do not care about taboo food.

↳ Sacred space(s)

– Yes

Notes: They do not observe a person while in the toilet.

↳ Sacred object(s)

– No

↳ Supernatural beings care about other

– Yes

Notes: Supernatural beings care about humans.

↳ Supernatural beings care about murder of coreligionists

– No

Notes: The text is silent on the murder of any personality.

↳ Supernatural beings care about murder of members of other religions

– No

Notes: The text did not extend discussion on the murder of any personality.

↳ Supernatural beings care about murder of members of other polities

– No

Notes: The text did not pay attention to the murder of members of other polities.

↳ Supernatural beings care about sex

– No

Notes: The text did not state the characteristics of supernatural beings.

- ↳ Supernatural beings care about lying
 - Yes
 - Notes: The text mentioned the prohibition of lying.
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about honouring oaths
 - Yes
 - Notes: The text commanded honoring the oath, which supernatural monitors set eyes on.
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about laziness
 - Yes
 - Notes: Supernatural beings record rewards for the devoted personality.
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about sorcery
 - No
 - Notes: Sorcery is prohibited by the religion of the text, hence supernatural monitors record it as sin against person to have done it.
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about non-lethal fighting
 - No
 - Notes: The text did not discuss non-lethal fighting.
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about shirking risk
 - No
 - Notes: The text did not describe supernatural beings.
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about disrespecting elders
 - Yes
 - Notes: But the text did not mention it.
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about gossiping
 - Yes
 - Notes: The text stated the prohibition of gossip.
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about property crimes
 - Yes
 - Notes: The text prohibited property crime.
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about proper ritual observance

– Yes

Notes: Supernatural beings care about ritual observance and hence record it as a reward to the person.

↳ Supernatural beings care about performance of rituals

– Yes

Notes: Supernatural beings attend places of ritual observance.

↳ Supernatural beings care about conversion of non-religionists

– Yes

Notes: Supernatural beings care about the conversion of non-religionist and hence record rewards on the person.

↳ Supernatural beings care about economic fairness

– Yes

Notes: Supernatural beings care about justice and fairness in economic dealings.

↳ Supernatural beings care about personal hygiene

– Yes

Notes: Supernatural beings care about personal hygiene, and the book expressed ablution as cleanliness to ensure personal hygiene.

↳ Supernatural beings care about or expect the maintenance of the place?

– Yes

Notes: The text recommended maintenance of the mosques for religious services, which are highly needed by supernatural beings.

↳ Supernatural beings care about other

– Specify: Supernatural beings care about others.

Is the text - or does the text include - a ritual list, manual, bibliography, index, or vocabulary?
(Select all that apply)

– Ritual manual

Notes: The text served as a manual to the ritual acts such prayer, ablution, bath etc.

Does the text require celibacy (full sexual abstinence)?

– No

Notes: The text forbids celibacy for people who have a legal spouse.

Are general social norms prescribed by the text?

– Yes

Notes: The text prescribed some social norms in the first three pages.

Are messianic beliefs present in the text?

– No

Notes: The text did not mention messianic beliefs.

Is the text itself accompanied by art?

– Yes

Notes: The text was concluded with a designated art on the last page.

Calligraphy?

– No

Notes: The designation of the last page was not a calligraphy.

Illustrations?

– Yes

Notes: The designation made on the last page was meant to indicate completion of discussion of the text.

Illuminations?

– No

Notes: It was just a designation.

Are there lineages or a single lineage established by the text?

– No

Notes: The text is for the entire Muslim community.

Is belief in an afterlife indicated in the text?

– Yes

Notes: The text indicated listed belief in the afterlife among the Islamic belief system.

Is the spatial location of the afterlife specified or described by the religious group?

– No

Notes: The location of the afterlife was not identified by the text.

Is the temporality of the afterlife specified or described by the religious group?

– No

Notes: The religious group ascertained its existence and reality.

↳ Is there debate in the interpretation of the language of the afterlife?

– No

Notes: The religious group in the sampled region accepted Arabic as the language of communication in the afterlife.

Does the text require constraints on sexual activity (partial sexual abstinence)?

– No

Notes: The text did not restrict lawful sexual activities.

Is there a conventional vs. moral distinction in the religious text?

– No

Notes: The text analyzed the only norms approved by Islam.

Is an eschatology present in the text?

– Yes

Notes: The text mentioned belief in some eschatological principles.

↳ Eschaton is in this lifetime

– No

Notes: Eschaton is in the afterlife.

↳ At specified time in future

– No

Notes: The time is not known to any except Allah.

↳ At unspecified time in near future

– No

Notes: The actual time is not known.

↳ At unspecified time in distant future

– No

Notes: The time remains secret to Allah alone.

↳ At some other time [specify]

– Yes

Notes: The time will be in the afterlife.

↳ Adherents need to perform specific tasks to bring about World's end

– No

Notes: Adherents do not influence the end of the world.

↳ Divine judgment event

– Yes

Notes: Divine judgment is to happen in the eschaton event.

↳ Restoration of the world

– No

Notes: A new world is to replace the existing one.

↳ Start of a new temporal cycle

– No

Notes: The eschaton marked the beginning of eternal life.

↳ Establishment of new political system

– No

Notes: The entire system belongs to Allah (the creator of all).

↳ Establishment of new religious system

– No

Notes: Religion is over by the end of the world.

↳ Other form of eschatology?

–Specify: Paradise, Hellfire, etc.

↳ Will anyone survive the eschaton?

– No

Notes: None survive the eschaton except God.

Do supernatural beings mete out punishment in the text?

– Yes

Notes: The text mentioned the punishment of supernatural beings in the hereafter against evil-doers.

↳ Is the cause or agent of supernatural punishment known?

– Yes

Notes: The cause of their punishment is disobedience to the directives of Allah (the High God)

↳ Done only by high god

– No

Notes: The punishment is done by angels on the directives of the high God.

↳ Done by many supernatural beings

– Yes

Notes: Many angels are assigned to punish the evil doers in the hereafter.

↳ Done through impersonal cause-effect principle

– Yes

Notes: The punishment is much more severe for the evildoers.

↳ Done by other entities or through other means

– No

Notes: The punishment is done by angels in the hellfire.

↳ Is the reason for supernatural punishment known?

– Yes

Notes: The cause of supernatural punishment is deviating from the shari'ah principles.

↳ Done to enforce religious ritual-devotional adherence?

– Yes

Notes: Adherents are to abide by Islamic law and do the rituals to escape punishment in the hereafter.

↳ Done to enforce group norms?

– Yes

Notes: The retributions are prearranged to enforce the religious norms of Islam.

↳ Done to inhibit selfishness?

– Yes

Notes: The punishment is reserved to make people avoid selfishness.

↳ Done randomly

– No

Notes: The punishment is done systematically on the sins of individuals.

↳ Other

– No

Notes: The punishment is done against those to have violated Islamic law.

↳ Supernatural punishments are meted out in the afterlife?

– Yes

Notes: The punishment is done in the afterlife.

↳ Highly emphasized by the religious group

– Yes

Notes: The religious group emphasized the punishment on the order of the Islamic religion.

↳ Punishments in the afterlife consists of mild sensory displeasure

– No

Notes: The punishment is severe.

↳ Punishment in the afterlife consists of extreme sensory displeasure?

– Yes

Notes: The punishment is excessively severe.

↳ Punishment in the afterlife consists of reincarnation as an inferior life form?

– No

Notes: There is no reincarnation in the religion of Islam.

↳ Punishment in the afterlife consists of reincarnation in an inferior realm?

– No

Notes: The punishment is beyond reincarnation in the inferior realm.

↳ Other form of punishment

– Specify: Painful burning in the hellfire.

↳ Supernatural punishments are meted out in this lifetime?

– No

Notes: Supernatural punishment is done in the afterlife.

Are there multiple versions of the text?

– Yes

Notes: The text had multiple versions, including printed copies, handwritten copies, and translations in other languages.

↳ Are multiple versions viewed as proper?

– Yes

Notes: Both versions are considered proper and correct.

↳ If multiple versions are proper, is there a differentiation among versions by any means?

– Yes

Notes: The versions are

↳ Age of extant version of text?

– Yes

Notes: Some versions might be older than others.

↳ Content of text?

– Yes

Notes: Some versions might have explanations, while some are even commentaries on the text.

↳ Ritual purpose of text?

– No

Notes: Versions are not prepared ritually.

↳ Is there debate about which version is proper?

– No

Notes: There is no debate about the multiple versions of the text.

Does the text require castration?

– No

Notes: The text prohibits castration.

Does the text express a formal legal code?

– No

Notes: The text guides religious rituals of prayer, ablution, bath, etc.

Is belief in reincarnation in this world specified in the text?

– No

Notes: The text did not mention belief in reincarnation in this world.

Is the text part of a collection of texts?

– No

Notes: The text was a single book.

Do supernatural beings bestow rewards in the text?

– No

Notes: The reward is only bestowed by God (Allah).

Are there centrally important virtues advocated by the text?

– Yes

Notes: The text advocated some norms and values that are vital in daily life.

↳ Honesty/trustworthiness/integrity

– Yes

Notes: The text recommended honesty.

↳ Courage (in battle)

– Yes

Notes: The text recommended courage.

↳ Courage (generic)

– Yes

Notes: The text instructed courage generally.

↳ Compassion/empathy/kindness/benevolence

– Yes

Notes: The text ordered Muslims towards kindness.

↳ Mercy/forgiveness/tolerance

– Yes

Notes: The text strongly advocated the habit of forgiveness.

↳ Generosity/charity

– Yes

Notes: The text urged believers to give out charity.

↳ Selflessness/selfless giving

– Yes

Notes: The text prohibited the habit of selfishness.

- ↳ Righteousness/moral rectitude
 - Yes
 - Notes: The text directed Muslims to be righteous in all their dealings.
- ↳ Ritual purity/ritual adherence/abstention from sources of impurity
 - Yes
 - Notes: The text separated subtopics for ritual purity.
- ↳ Respectfulness/courtesy
 - Yes
 - Notes: The text directed Muslims on respectfulness to others.
- ↳ Familial obedience/filial piety
 - Yes
 - Notes: The text advocated piety in all affairs.
- ↳ Fidelity/loyalty
 - Yes
 - Notes: The text required Muslims to remain loyal to the directives of Shari'ah.
- ↳ Cooperation
 - Yes
 - Notes: The text advocated unity and cooperation among Muslims.
- ↳ Independence/creativity/freedom
 - Yes
 - Notes: The text recommends Muslims to be creative in life.
- ↳ Moderation/frugality
 - Yes
 - Notes: The text called for frugality.
- ↳ Forbearance/fortitude/patience
 - Yes
 - Notes: The text recommends bits of patience.
- ↳ Diligence/self-discipline/excellence
 - Yes

Notes: The text ordered Muslims to self-discipline.

↳ Assertiveness/decisiveness/confidence/initiative

– Yes

Notes: The text guides to assertiveness.

↳ Strength (physical)

– Yes

Notes: The text recommends strength to believers.

↳ Power/status/nobility

– Yes

Notes: The text recommends Muslims not remain weak.

↳ Humility/modesty

– Yes

Notes: The text called for modesty in life.

↳ Contentment/serenity/equanimity

– Yes

Notes: The text prohibits greediness.

↳ Joyfulness/enthusiasm/cheerfulness

– Yes

Notes: The text recommends Muslims to be enthusiastic in life.

↳ Optimism/hope

– Yes

Notes: The text directed Muslims to set hope in Alla's assistance.

↳ Gratitude/thankfulness

– Yes

Notes: The text ordered gratitude behavior.

↳ Reverence/awe/wonder

– Yes

Notes: The text called for reverence.

↳ Faith/belief/trust/devotion

– Yes

Notes: The text ordered Muslims to set trust in Allah.

↳ Wisdom/understanding

– Yes

Notes: The text ordered Muslims to pursue wisdom wherever they found it.

↳ Discernment/intelligence

– Yes

Notes: The text recommended intelligence.

↳ Beauty/attractiveness

– Yes

Notes: The text recommends cleanliness to have beauty.

↳ Cleanliness (physical)/orderliness

– Yes

Notes: The text ordered Muslims to cleanliness.

↳ Other important virtues

– Yes

Notes: The text ordered devotion in worship.

Does the text require fasting?

– Yes

Notes: The text directed Muslims to fast in the month of Ramadan.

Are there special treatments for adherents' corpses dictated in the text?

– No

Notes: The text did not discuss funeral services.

If the text is not explicitly scripture, is it part of another important literary tradition?

– Yes

Notes: The text is part of the Islamic jurisprudential books.

↳ Cultural with religious implications?

– Yes

Notes: The text is part of the Islamic culture of performing religious duties.

Behavioral literature?

– Yes

Notes: The text made explanation on how Muslims shall behave.

Other

–Other [specify]: Islamic principles

Formulating a specifically religious calendar?

– No

Notes: The text did not formulate a religious calendar but operated on the Islamic lunar calendar.

Does the text indicate if co-sacrifices should be present in burials?

– No

Notes: Co-sacrifices are not accepted in the religion of the text.

Does the text require forgone food opportunities (taboos on desired foods)?

– No

Notes: The text did not require forgone food opportunities.

Does the text require permanent scarring or painful bodily alterations?

– No

Notes: The text does not require permanent scarring.

Does the text specify grave goods for burial?

– No

Notes: The religion of the text did not allow any goods to be buried along with corps.

Are formal burials present in the text?

– No

Notes: The text had not extended the discussion on burials.

Does the text require painful physical positions or transitory painful wounds?

– No

Notes: The text did not require a painful wound.

Does the text require sacrifice of adults?

– No

Notes: The text prohibits the sacrifice of adults.

Are there practices that have funerary associations presented in the text?

– No

Notes: The text did not discuss issues related to funeral services.

Are supernatural beings present in the text?

– Yes

Notes: The text mentioned belief in the supernatural being, especially belief in Allah (the creator).

↳ A supreme high-god is present

– Yes

Notes: The text mentioned the Supreme High God.

↳ The supreme high god is anthropomorphic or described in anthropomorphic terms

– No

Notes: The nature of the supreme high God is beyond description.

↳ The supreme high god is a sky deity

– Yes

Notes: The Supreme high God is the sky deity.

↳ The supreme high god is chthonic (of the underworld)

– No

Notes: Supreme high God has control over the underworld without dwelling in it.

↳ The supreme high god is fused with the monarch (king=high god)

– No

Notes: The supreme high God has control over the monarch.

↳ The monarch is seen as a manifestation or emanation of the high god

– No

Notes: The monarch is only viewed as a servant of the supreme high God.

↳ The supreme high god is a kin relation to elites

– No

Notes: Elites ought to obey the directives of the supreme high God.

↳ The supreme high god has another type of loyalty-connection to elites

– No

Notes: No relation apart from the creator and created.

↳ The supreme high god is unquestionably good

– Yes

Notes: The supreme high God is unquestionably good.

↳ Other features of the supreme high god

– Specify: Supreme high God designs the destiny of every created being.

↳ The supreme high god has knowledge of this world

– Yes

Notes: Nothing escapes the knowledge of the high God.

↳ Knowledge is restricted to a particular domain of human affairs

– No

Notes: Knowledge of the supreme high God extends to the entire life affairs of humans.

↳ Knowledge is restricted to (a) specific area(s) within the sample region

– No

Notes: Knowledge of the supreme high is beyond restriction on a particular domain.

↳ Knowledge is unrestricted within the sample region

– Yes

Notes: Knowledge of the supreme high God extends to the entire world.

↳ Knowledge is unrestrict outside of sample region

– Yes

Notes: Knowledge of the supreme high God is unrestricted outside the sampled region.

↳ Can see you everywhere normally visible (in public)

– Yes

Notes: Supreme high God can see everyone anywhere.

↳ Can see you everywhere (in the dark, at home)

– Yes

Notes: Supreme high God can see everyone in all places.

↳ Can see inside heart/mind (hidden motives)

– Yes

Notes: Supreme high God knows what is hidden in the mind.

↳ Knows basic character (personal essence)

– Yes

Notes: Supreme high God knows the personal essence of humans.

↳ Knows what will happen to you, what you will do (future sight)

– Yes

Notes: Supreme high God knows what is to happen in the future.

↳ Has other knowledge of this world

– Yes

Notes: Supreme high God has the entire knowledge of the world.

↳ Has deliberate causal efficacy in the world

– Yes

Notes: Supreme high God has the power to cause everything in this world.

↳ Can reward

– Yes

Notes: Supreme high God can reward on good deeds of humans in this world.

↳ Can punish

– Yes

Notes: Supreme high God can punish the wrong deeds of humans.

↳ Indirect causal efficacy in the world

– Yes

Notes: Supreme high God may indirectly cause efficacy in this world.

↳ Exhibits positive emotion

– No

Notes: Supreme high God could not be displayed.

- ↳ Exhibits negative emotion
 - No
 - Notes: Negative emotions of the high God are not merely displayed.

- ↳ Possesses Hunger?
 - No
 - Notes: Supreme high God has no desire for food.

- ↳ Can be hurt?
 - No
 - Notes: Supreme high God cannot be hurt.

- ↳ Can be tricked?
 - No
 - Notes: None can trich the supreme High God.

- ↳ Can be imprisoned?
 - No
 - Notes: Supreme High God cannot be imprisoned.

- ↳ Is it permissible to worship supernatural being other than the high god?
 - No
 - Notes: None is allowed to be worshiped apart from the supreme High God (Allah).

- ↳ The supreme high god possesses/exhibits some other feature
 - Specify: Supreme High God created the world and what is inside it.

- ↳ The supreme high god communicates with the living
 - Yes
 - Notes: Supreme High God communicates with humans through special messengers.

- ↳ In waking, everday life
 - Yes
 - Notes: Through the messengers.

- ↳ In dreams
 - Yes
 - Notes: If he so wishes.

↳ In trance possession

– Yes

Notes: If he desired that.

↳ Through divination practices

– No

Notes: Divine practices do not make one communicate with the supreme High God.

↳ Only through religious specialists

– Yes

Notes: Especially messengers.

↳ Only through monarch

– No

Notes: Through messengers.

↳ Other form of communication with living

– Yes

Notes: Revelation.

↳ Does the text make communication with supreme high-god possible?

– No

Notes: The text only guides on how to worship him.

Does the text require sacrifice of children?

– No

Notes: The text prohibits the sacrifice of children.

Previously human spirits are present

– Yes

Notes: The human spirit was mentioned in the text.

↳ Human spirits can be seen

– No

Notes: The human spirit cannot be seen.

↳ Human spirits can be physically felt

– No

Notes: The presence of the human spirit cannot be felt physically.

↳ Previously human spirits have knowledge of this world

– Yes

Notes: The human spirit is aware of this world.

↳ Knowledge is restricted to a particular domain of human affairs

– No

Notes: Its knowledge is not restricted to a particular domain.

↳ Knowledge is restricted to (a) specific area(s) within the sample region

– No

Notes: Knowledge of the human spirit extends beyond the sampled region.

↳ Knowledge is unrestricted within the sample region

– Yes

Notes: Knowledge of the human spirit is not restricted within the sampled region.

↳ Knowledge is unrestricted outside of sample region

– Yes

Notes: Knowledge of the human spirit is not restricted outside the sampled region.

↳ Can see you everywhere normally visible (in public)

– Yes

Notes: The human spirit accompanies its body everywhere.

↳ Can see you everywhere (in the dark, at home)

– Yes

Notes: It can see you everywhere.

↳ Can see inside heart/mind (hidden motives)

– No

Notes: It does not have the power of knowing what is hidden in the mind.

↳ Know basic character (personal essence)

– Yes

Notes: It knows fundamental personal essence.

↳ Know what will happen to you, what you will do (future sight)

– No

Notes: It does not know the future.

↳ Have other knowledge of this world

– Specify: It knows other creatures around the man.

↳ Human spirits have deliberate causal efficacy in the world

– No

Notes: It does not have deliberate causal efficacy in the world.

↳ Human spirits have indirect causal efficacy in the world

– No

Notes: It does not cause efficacy of the world directly or indirectly.

↳ Human spirits have memory of life

– Yes

Notes: It has a memory of the life after the death of its accompanied body.

↳ Human spirits exhibit positive emotion

– No

Notes: It does not exhibit positive emotion.

↳ Human spirits exhibit negative emotion

– No

Notes: It does not exhibit negative emotions.

↳ Human spirits communicate with the living

– Yes

Notes: It communicates with the body through dream experiences.

↳ In waking, everyday life

– No

Notes: It does not communicate in awake situations.

↳ In dreams

– Yes

Notes: It communicates in dream situations.

↳ In trance possession

– No

↳ Through divination practices

– No

Notes: Divine practices do not attract communication with the human spirit.

↳ Only through religious specialists

– No

Notes: Communication with the human spirit is not possible through religious specialists.

↳ Only through monarch

– No

Notes: Monarchs do not communicate with the human spirit.

↳ Communicate through other means

– Specify: Only through dream alone.

Does the text require self-sacrifice (suicide)?

– No

Notes: The text does not require suicide.

Non-human supernatural beings are present

– Yes

Notes: Angels are present in the text.

↳ Supernatural beings can be seen

– No

Notes: Angels might not necessarily be seen except when ones dies.

↳ Supernatural beings can be physically felt

– No

Notes: Human beings do not feel them physically.

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge of this world

– Yes

Notes: Nonhuman supernatural beings know this world.

- ↳ Knowledge is restricted to a particular domain of human affairs
 - No
 - Notes: Their knowledge extends to human affairs except for what is hidden in the mind.
- ↳ Knowledge is restricted to (a) specific area(s) within the sample region
 - No
 - Notes: Their knowledge is not restricted within the sampled region.
- ↳ Knowledge is unrestricted within the sample region
 - Yes
- ↳ Knowledge is unrestricted outside of sample region
 - Yes
 - Notes: Their knowledge might extend everywhere outside the sampled region.
- ↳ Can see you everywhere normally visible (in public)
 - Yes
 - Notes: They can see humans in public.
- ↳ Can see you everywhere (in the dark, at home)
 - Yes
 - Notes: They can see humans everywhere.
- ↳ Can see inside heart/mind (hidden motives)
 - No
 - Notes: They do not see the hidden motive of humans.
- ↳ Know basic character (personal essence)
 - Yes
 - Notes: They know the characteristics of humans.
- ↳ Know what will happen to you, what you will do (future sight)
 - No
 - Notes: Knowledge of the future is only limited to God.
- ↳ Have other knowledge of this world
 - Yes
 - Notes: They have other knowledge of the world.

- ↳ Non-human supernatural beings have deliberate causal efficacy in the world
 - No
 - Notes: Non-human supernatural beings do not cause efficacy in the world.

- ↳ Non-human supernatural beings communicate with the living according to the text?
 - Yes
 - Notes: Non-human supernatural beings communicate with humans on the directives of God.

 - ↳ In waking, everyday life?
 - Yes
 - Notes: Non-human supernatural beings communicate to prophets.

 - ↳ In dreams?
 - Yes
 - Notes: Non-human supernatural beings communicate through dreams.

 - ↳ In trance possession?
 - Yes
 - Notes: Non-human supernatural beings might communicate in trance possession.

 - ↳ Through divination practices?
 - No
 - Notes: Divine practices do not lead to on-human supernatural beings' communication.

 - ↳ Only through religious specialists?
 - Yes
 - Notes: Non-human supernatural beings communicate to prophets.

 - ↳ Only through monarch?
 - No
 - Notes: Non-human supernatural beings do not communicate through monarchs.

 - ↳ Other?
 - Specify: Not really stated in the text.

- ↳ These supernatural beings have indirect causal efficacy in the world
 - No
 - Notes: Non-human supernatural beings do not (indirectly) cause efficacy in the world.

↳ These supernatural beings exhibit positive emotion

– No

Notes: Non-human supernatural beings do not exhibit positive emotions.

↳ These supernatural beings exhibit negative emotion

– No

Notes: Non-human supernatural beings do not exhibit negative emotions.

↳ These supernatural beings possess hunger

– No

Notes: Angels do not have a desire for food.

↳ These supernatural beings possess/exhibit some other feature

–Specify: Supernatural beings have the power to move from one place to another.

Does the text require sacrifice of property/valuable items?

– Yes

Notes: The text recommends the sacrifice of properties for charity.

Does the text require sacrifice of time (e.g. attendance at meetings or services, regular prayer, etc.)?

– Yes

Notes: The text directed for the sacrifice of time to attend a congregation of the five daily prayers.

Does the text attest to a pantheon of supernatural beings?

– No

Notes: The text rejected the existence of the pantheon of supernatural beings.

Are mixed human-divine beings present according to the text?

– No

Notes: The text did not mention the existence of mixed human-divine beings.

Does the text require physical risk taking?

– No

Notes: The text did not require risk-taking that might lead to the loss of life without due cause.

Is there a supernatural being that is physically present in the/as a result of the text?

– No

Notes: The text does not attract the presence of any supernatural being.

Does the text require accepting ethical precepts?

– Yes

Notes: The text requires acceptance of ethical precepts that fulfilled the directives of Islam.

Are other categories of beings present?

– Other [specify]: Jinns

Does the text require marginalization by out-group members?

– No

Notes: The text called for unity.

Does the text guide divination practices?

– No

Notes: The text guide on worshiping Allah through prayers.

Does the text require participation in small-scale rituals (private, household)?

– Yes

Notes: The text requires the attendance of prayer services.

What is the average interval of time between performances?

–Hours: 2

Does the text require participation in large-scale rituals?

– Yes

Notes: The text requires attendance of large-scale rituals on Friday and Eid occasions.

On average, how many participants gather in one location?

–Number of participants: 1000

Notes: The number begins from twelve people to unlimited.

Interval of time between performances (in hours)

–Hours: 168

Notes: For the performance of the weekly Friday prayer.

Are there orthodoxy checks?

– Yes

Are there orthopraxy checks?

– No

↳ Does participation entail synchronic practices?

– Yes

Notes: The rituals are stipulated for a particular period.

↳ Is there use of intoxicants?

– No

Notes: The text prohibits the use of intoxicants.

Are extra-ritual in-group markers present as indicated in the text?

– No

Notes: The text does not require grouping in the extra ritual activities.

Does the text employ fictive kinship terminology?

– No

Notes: The text rejects fictive terminology.

Does the text include elements that are intended to be entertaining?

– No

Notes: The text did not employ entertainment elements.

Does the text specify sacrifices, offerings, and maintenance of a sacred space?

– Yes

Notes: The text requires the sacrifice of animals on Eid Day.

↳ Are sacrifices specified by the text?

– Yes

↳ Animal sacrifice?

– Yes

Notes: The text is directed toward the sacrifice of animals on Eid day.

↳ Human sacrifice?

– No

Notes: The text prohibits the sacrifice of humans.

↳ Are there self-sacrifices specified by the text?

– No

Notes: The text does not require self-sacrifice.

↳ Are there material offerings present?

– Yes

Notes: The text called for material offerings.

↳ Are they mandatory?

– Yes

Notes: The text directed material offerings in the form of obligatory charity (Zakat) on those having the due amount of the charity.

↳ Are they composed of valuable objects?

– Yes

Notes: They compose money, precious stones, animals, and crops.

↳ Are they composed of daily-life objects?

– Yes

Notes: Especially crops and animals.

↳ Are material offerings interred at this place (in caches)?

– No

Notes: The materials are given to poor people.

↳ Are there particular smells associated with material offerings?

– No

Notes: No smell is required on the materials.

↳ Are there particular visual stimuli (colors, symbols) associated with the offerings? (I.e. 'must be bright' 'must include red')

– No

Notes: The materials must be valuable alone.

↳ Other?

– Specify: The materials must not have defects.

↳ Is attendance to worship/sacrifice mandatory?

– No

Notes: Attendance of sacrifice is not mandatory.

↳ Is the maintenance of the place regulated by the text?

– Yes

Notes: The text recommended maintainance of the places of worships.

↳ Is it required?

– Yes

Notes: Maintainance of the place is required.

↳ Is there cleansing (for the maintenance)?

– Yes

Notes: The text orders the cleaning of the mosques.

↳ Are there periodic repairs/reconstructions?

– No

Notes: The text did not specify the time of maintenance to the place.

↳ Is the maintenance performed by permanent staff?

– No

Notes: Maintenance is voluntary.

↳ Other?

– Specify: All sorts of dirt must be kept away from the place.

Context

Is the text itself accompanied by art?

– Yes

Notes: The text was concluded with a designated art on the last page.

↳ Calligraphy?

– No

Notes: The designation of the last page was not a calligraphy.

↳ Illustrations?

– Yes

Notes: The designation made on the last page was meant to indicate completion of discussion of the text.

↳ Illuminations?

– No

Notes: It was just a designation.

Are there multiple versions of the text?

– Yes

Notes: The text had multiple versions, including printed copies, handwritten copies, and translations in other languages.

↳ Are multiple versions viewed as proper?

– Yes

Notes: Both versions are considered proper and correct.

↳ If multiple versions are proper, is there a differentiation among versions by any means?

– Yes

Notes: The versions are

↳ Age of extant version of text?

– Yes

Notes: Some versions might be older than others.

↳ Content of text?

– Yes

Notes: Some versions might have explanations, while some are even commentaries on the text.

↳ Ritual purpose of text?

– No

Notes: Versions are not prepared ritually.

↳ Is there debate about which version is proper?

– No

Notes: There is no debate about the multiple versions of the text.

Is the text part of a collection of texts?

– No

Notes: The text was a single book.

If the text is not explicitly scripture, is it part of another important literary tradition?

– Yes

Notes: The text is part of the Islamic jurisprudential books.

↳ Cultural with religious implications?

– Yes

Notes: The text is part of the Islamic culture of performing religious duties.

↳ Behavioral literature?

– Yes

Notes: The text made explanation on how Muslims shall behave.

↳ Other

– Other [specify]: Islamic principles

Content

Is the text - or does the text include - a ritual list, manual, bibliography, index, or vocabulary?
(Select all that apply)

– Ritual manual

Notes: The text served as a manual to the ritual acts such prayer, ablution, bath etc.

Are there lineages or a single lineage established by the text?

– No

Notes: The text is for the entire Muslim community.

Does the text express a formal legal code?

– No

Notes: The text guides religious rituals of prayer, ablution, bath, etc.

Formulating a specifically religious calendar?

– No

Notes: The text did not formulate a religious calendar but operated on the Islamic lunar calendar.

Beliefs

Is a spirit-body distinction present in the text?

– No

Notes: The text did not make a spirit-body distinction.

Is belief in an afterlife indicated in the text?

– Yes

Notes: The text indicated listed belief in the afterlife among the Islamic belief system.

↳ Is the spatial location of the afterlife specified or described by the religious group?

– No

Notes: The location of the afterlife was not identified by the text.

↳ Is the temporality of the afterlife specified or described by the religious group?

– No

Notes: The religious group ascertained its existence and reality.

↳ Is there debate in the interpretation of the language of the afterlife?

– No

Notes: The religious group in the sampled region accepted Arabic as the language of communication in the afterlife.

Is belief in reincarnation in this world specified in the text?

– No

Notes: The text did not mention belief in reincarnation in this world.

Are there special treatments for adherents' corpses dicated in the text?

– No

Notes: The text did not discuss funeral services.

Does the text indicate if co-sacrifices should be present in burials?

– No

Notes: Co-sacrifices are not accepted in the religion of the text.

Does the text specify grave goods for burial?

– No

Notes: The religion of the text did not allow any goods to be buried along with corps.

Are formal burials present in the text?

– No

Notes: The text had not extended the discussion on burials.

Are there practices that have funerary associations presented in the text?

– No

Notes: The text did not discuss issues related to funeral services.

Are supernatural beings present in the text?

– Yes

Notes: The text mentioned belief in the supernatural being, especially belief in Allah (the creator).

↳ A supreme high-god is present

– Yes

Notes: The text mentioned the Supreme High God.

↳ The supreme high god is anthropomorphic or described in anthropomorphic terms

– No

Notes: The nature of the supreme high God is beyond description.

↳ The supreme high god is a sky deity

– Yes

Notes: The Supreme high God is the sky deity.

↳ The supreme high god is chthonic (of the underworld)

– No

Notes: Supreme high God has control over the underworld without dwelling in it.

↳ The supreme high god is fused with the monarch (king=high god)

– No

Notes: The supreme high God has control over the monarch.

↳ The monarch is seen as a manifestation or emanation of the high god

– No

Notes: The monarch is only viewed as a servant of the supreme high God.

↳ The supreme high god is a kin relation to elites

– No

Notes: Elites ought to obey the directives of the supreme high God.

↳ The supreme high god has another type of loyalty-connection to elites

– No

Notes: No relation apart from the creator and created.

- ↳ The supreme high god is unquestionably good
 - Yes
 - Notes: The supreme high God is unquestionably good.

- ↳ Other features of the supreme high god
 - Specify: Supreme high God designs the destiny of every created being.

- ↳ The supreme high god has knowledge of this world
 - Yes
 - Notes: Nothing escapes the knowledge of the high God.

- ↳ Knowledge is restricted to a particular domain of human affairs
 - No
 - Notes: Knowledge of the supreme high God extends to the entire life affairs of humans.

- ↳ Knowledge is restricted to (a) specific area(s) within the sample region
 - No
 - Notes: Knowledge of the supreme high is beyond restriction on a particular domain.

- ↳ Knowledge is unrestricted within the sample region
 - Yes
 - Notes: Knowledge of the supreme high God extends to the entire world.

- ↳ Knowledge is unrestrict outside of sample region
 - Yes
 - Notes: Knowledge of the supreme high God is unrestricted outside the sampled region.

- ↳ Can see you everywhere normally visible (in public)
 - Yes
 - Notes: Supreme high God can see everyone anywhere.

- ↳ Can see you everywhere (in the dark, at home)
 - Yes
 - Notes: Supreme high God can see everyone in all places.

- ↳ Can see inside heart/mind (hidden motives)

– Yes

Notes: Supreme high God knows what is hidden in the mind.

↳ Knows basic character (personal essence)

– Yes

Notes: Supreme high God knows the personal essence of humans.

↳ Knows what will happen to you, what you will do (future sight)

– Yes

Notes: Supreme high God knows what is to happen in the future.

↳ Has other knowledge of this world

– Yes

Notes: Supreme high God has the entire knowledge of the world.

↳ Has deliberate causal efficacy in the world

– Yes

Notes: Supreme high God has the power to cause everything in this world.

↳ Can reward

– Yes

Notes: Supreme high God can reward on good deeds of humans in this world.

↳ Can punish

– Yes

Notes: Supreme high God can punish the wrong deeds of humans.

↳ Indirect causal efficacy in the world

– Yes

Notes: Supreme high God may indirectly cause efficacy in this world.

↳ Exhibits positive emotion

– No

Notes: Supreme high God could not be displayed.

↳ Exhibits negative emotion

– No

Notes: Negative emotions of the high God are not merely displayed.

- ↳ Possesses Hunger?
 - No
 - Notes: Supreme high God has no desire for food.

- ↳ Can be hurt?
 - No
 - Notes: Supreme high God cannot be hurt.

- ↳ Can be tricked?
 - No
 - Notes: None can trich the supreme High God.

- ↳ Can be imprisoned?
 - No
 - Notes: Supreme High God cannot be imprisoned.

- ↳ Is it permissible to worship supernatural being other than the high god?
 - No
 - Notes: None is allowed to be worshiped apart from the supreme High God (Allah).

- ↳ The supreme high god possesses/exhibits some other feature
 - Specify: Supreme High God created the world and what is inside it.

- ↳ The supreme high god communicates with the living
 - Yes
 - Notes: Supreme High God communicates with humans through special messengers.
 - ↳ In waking, everday life
 - Yes
 - Notes: Through the messengers.

 - ↳ In dreams
 - Yes
 - Notes: If he so wishes.

 - ↳ In trance possession
 - Yes
 - Notes: If he desired that.

↳ Through divination practices

– No

Notes: Divine practices do not make one communicate with the supreme High God.

↳ Only through religious specialists

– Yes

Notes: Especially messengers.

↳ Only through monarch

– No

Notes: Through messengers.

↳ Other form of communication with living

– Yes

Notes: Revelation.

↳ Does the text make communication with supreme high-god possible?

– No

Notes: The text only guides on how to worship him.

Previously human spirits are present

– Yes

Notes: The human spirit was mentioned in the text.

↳ Human spirits can be seen

– No

Notes: The human spirit cannot be seen.

↳ Human spirits can be physically felt

– No

Notes: The presence of the human spirit cannot be felt physically.

↳ Previously human spirits have knowledge of this world

– Yes

Notes: The human spirit is aware of this world.

↳ Knowledge is restricted to a particular domain of human affairs

– No

Notes: Its knowledge is not restricted to a particular domain.

↳ Knowledge is restricted to (a) specific area(s) within the sample region

– No

Notes: Knowledge of the human spirit extends beyond the sampled region.

↳ Knowledge is unrestricted within the sample region

– Yes

Notes: Knowledge of the human spirit is not restricted within the sampled region.

↳ Knowledge is unrestricted outside of sample region

– Yes

Notes: Knowledge of the human spirit is not restricted outside the sampled region.

↳ Can see you everywhere normally visible (in public)

– Yes

Notes: The human spirit accompanies its body everywhere.

↳ Can see you everywhere (in the dark, at home)

– Yes

Notes: It can see you everywhere.

↳ Can see inside heart/mind (hidden motives)

– No

Notes: It does not have the power of knowing what is hidden in the mind.

↳ Know basic character (personal essence)

– Yes

Notes: It knows fundamental personal essence.

↳ Know what will happen to you, what you will do (future sight)

– No

Notes: It does not know the future.

↳ Have other knowledge of this world

– Specify: It knows other creatures around the man.

↳ Human spirits have deliberate causal efficacy in the world

– No

Notes: It does not have deliberate causal efficacy in the world.

↳ Human spirits have indirect causal efficacy in the world

– No

Notes: It does not cause efficacy of the world directly or indirectly.

↳ Human spirits have memory of life

– Yes

Notes: It has a memory of the life after the death of its accompanied body.

↳ Human spirits exhibit positive emotion

– No

Notes: It does not exhibit positive emotion.

↳ Human spirits exhibit negative emotion

– No

Notes: It does not exhibit negative emotions.

↳ Human spirits communicate with the living

– Yes

Notes: It communicates with the body through dream experiences.

↳ In waking, everyday life

– No

Notes: It does not communicate in awake situations.

↳ In dreams

– Yes

Notes: It communicates in dream situations.

↳ In trance possession

– No

↳ Through divination practices

– No

Notes: Divine practices do not attract communication with the human spirit.

↳ Only through religious specialists

– No

Notes: Communication with the human spirit is not possible through religious specialists.

↳ Only through monarch

– No

Notes: Monarchs do not communicate with the human spirit.

↳ Communicate through other means

– Specify: Only through dream alone.

Non-human supernatural beings are present

– Yes

Notes: Angels are present in the text.

↳ Supernatural beings can be seen

– No

Notes: Angels might not necessarily be seen except when ones dies.

↳ Supernatural beings can be physically felt

– No

Notes: Human beings do not feel them physically.

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge of this world

– Yes

Notes: Nonhuman supernatural beings know this world.

↳ Knowledge is restricted to a particular domain of human affairs

– No

Notes: Their knowledge extends to human affairs except for what is hidden in the mind.

↳ Knowledge is restricted to (a) specific area(s) within the sample region

– No

Notes: Their knowledge is not restricted within the sampled region.

↳ Knowledge is unrestricted within the sample region

– Yes

↳ Knowledge is unrestricted outside of sample region
– Yes
Notes: Their knowledge might extend everywhere outside the sampled region.

↳ Can see you everywhere normally visible (in public)
– Yes
Notes: They can see humans in public.

↳ Can see you everywhere (in the dark, at home)
– Yes
Notes: They can see humans everywhere.

↳ Can see inside heart/mind (hidden motives)
– No
Notes: They do not see the hidden motive of humans.

↳ Know basic character (personal essence)
– Yes
Notes: They know the characteristics of humans.

↳ Know what will happen to you, what you will do (future sight)
– No
Notes: Knowledge of the future is only limited to God.

↳ Have other knowledge of this world
– Yes
Notes: They have other knowledge of the world.

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have deliberate causal efficacy in the world
– No
Notes: Non-human supernatural beings do not cause efficacy in the world.

↳ Non-human supernatural beings communicate with the living according to the text?
– Yes
Notes: Non-human supernatural beings communicate with humans on the directives of God.

↳ In waking, everyday life?
– Yes

Notes: Non-human supernatural beings communicate to prophets.

↳ In dreams?

– Yes

Notes: Non-human supernatural beings communicate through dreams.

↳ In trance possession?

– Yes

Notes: Non-human supernatural beings might communicate in trance possession.

↳ Through divination practices?

– No

Notes: Divine practices do not lead to on-human supernatural beings' communication.

↳ Only through religious specialists?

– Yes

Notes: Non-human supernatural beings communicate to prophets.

↳ Only through monarch?

– No

Notes: Non-human supernatural beings do not communicate through monarchs.

↳ Other?

– Specify: Not really stated in the text.

↳ These supernatural beings have indirect causal efficacy in the world

– No

Notes: Non-human supernatural beings do not (indirectly) cause efficacy in the world.

↳ These supernatural beings exhibit positive emotion

– No

Notes: Non-human supernatural beings do not exhibit positive emotions.

↳ These supernatural beings exhibit negative emotion

– No

Notes: Non-human supernatural beings do not exhibit negative emotions.

↳ These supernatural beings possess hunger

– No

Notes: Angels do not have a desire for food.

These supernatural beings possess/exhibit some other feature

– Specify: Supernatural beings have the power to move from one place to another.

Does the text attest to a pantheon of supernatural beings?

– No

Notes: The text rejected the existence of the pantheon of supernatural beings.

Are mixed human-divine beings present according to the text?

– No

Notes: The text did not mention the existence of mixed human-divine beings.

Is there a supernatural being that is physically present in the/as a result of the text?

– No

Notes: The text does not attract the presence of any supernatural being.

Are other categories of beings present?

– Other [specify]: Jinns

Does the text guide divination practices?

– No

Notes: The text guide on worshipping Allah through prayers.

Supernatural Monitoring

Is supernatural monitoring present in the text?

– Yes

Notes: The text emphasized sincerity in worshipping Allah for his observance of human activities.

There is supernatural monitoring of prosocial norm adherence in particular

– Yes

Notes: The text stated monitoring of angels to human activities.

Do expectations of ritual offerings play a role in supernatural monitoring?

– No

Notes: Ritual expectations do not attract divine monitoring.

↳ Supernatural being care about taboos
– Yes
Notes: Supernatural beings do not appear before a naked person.

↳ Food
– No
Notes: They do not care about taboo food.

↳ Sacred space(s)
– Yes
Notes: They do not observe a person while in the toilet.

↳ Sacred object(s)
– No

↳ Supernatural beings care about other
– Yes
Notes: Supernatural beings care about humans.

↳ Supernatural beings care about murder of coreligionists
– No
Notes: The text is silent on the murder of any personality.

↳ Supernatural beings care about murder of members of other religions
– No
Notes: The text did not extend discussion on the murder of any personality.

↳ Supernatural beings care about murder of members of other polities
– No
Notes: The text did not pay attention to the murder of members of other polities.

↳ Supernatural beings care about sex
– No
Notes: The text did not state the characteristics of supernatural beings.

↳ Supernatural beings care about lying
– Yes
Notes: The text mentioned the prohibition of lying.

- ↳ Supernatural beings care about honouring oaths
 - Yes
 - Notes: The text commanded honoring the oath, which supernatural monitors set eyes on.
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about laziness
 - Yes
 - Notes: Supernatural beings record rewards for the devoted personality.
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about sorcery
 - No
 - Notes: Sorcery is prohibited by the religion of the text, hence supernatural monitors record it as sin against person to have done it.
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about non-lethal fighting
 - No
 - Notes: The text did not discuss non-lethal fighting.
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about shirking risk
 - No
 - Notes: The text did not describe supernatural beings.
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about disrespecting elders
 - Yes
 - Notes: But the text did not mention it.
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about gossiping
 - Yes
 - Notes: The text stated the prohibition of gossip.
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about property crimes
 - Yes
 - Notes: The text prohibited property crime.
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about proper ritual observance
 - Yes
 - Notes: Supernatural beings care about ritual observance and hence record it as a reward to the person.
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about performance of rituals

– Yes

Notes: Supernatural beings attend places of ritual observance.

↳ Supernatural beings care about conversion of non-religionists

– Yes

Notes: Supernatural beings care about the conversion of non-religionist and hence record rewards on the person.

↳ Supernatural beings care about economic fairness

– Yes

Notes: Supernatural beings care about justice and fairness in economic dealings.

↳ Supernatural beings care about personal hygiene

– Yes

Notes: Supernatural beings care about personal hygiene, and the book expressed ablution as cleanliness to ensure personal hygiene.

↳ Supernatural beings care about or expect the maintenance of the place?

– Yes

Notes: The text recommended maintenance of the mosques for religious services, which are highly needed by supernatural beings.

↳ Supernatural beings care about other

– Specify: Supernatural beings care about others.

Do supernatural beings mete out punishment in the text?

– Yes

Notes: The text mentioned the punishment of supernatural beings in the hereafter against evil-doers.

↳ Is the cause or agent of supernatural punishment known?

– Yes

Notes: The cause of their punishment is disobedience to the directives of Allah (the High God)

↳ Done only by high god

– No

Notes: The punishment is done by angels on the directives of the high God.

↳ Done by many supernatural beings

– Yes

Notes: Many angels are assigned to punish the evil doers in the hereafter.

↳ Done through impersonal cause-effect principle

– Yes

Notes: The punishment is much more severe for the evildoers.

↳ Done by other entities or through other means

– No

Notes: The punishment is done by angels in the hellfire.

↳ Is the reason for supernatural punishment known?

– Yes

Notes: The cause of supernatural punishment is deviating from the shari'ah principles.

↳ Done to enforce religious ritual-devotional adherence?

– Yes

Notes: Adherents are to abide by Islamic law and do the rituals to escape punishment in the hereafter.

↳ Done to enforce group norms?

– Yes

Notes: The retributions are prearranged to enforce the religious norms of Islam.

↳ Done to inhibit selfishness?

– Yes

Notes: The punishment is reserved to make people avoid selfishness.

↳ Done randomly

– No

Notes: The punishment is done systematically on the sins of individuals.

↳ Other

– No

Notes: The punishment is done against those to have violated Islamic law.

↳ Supernatural punishments are meted out in the afterlife?

– Yes

Notes: The punishment is done in the afterlife.

↳ Highly emphasized by the religious group

– Yes

Notes: The religious group emphasized the punishment on the order of the Islamic religion.

↳ Punishments in the afterlife consists of mild sensory displeasure

– No

Notes: The punishment is severe.

↳ Punishment in the afterlife consists of extreme sensory displeasure?

– Yes

Notes: The punishment is excessively severe.

↳ Punishment in the afterlife consists of reincarnation as an inferior life form?

– No

Notes: There is no reincarnation in the religion of Islam.

↳ Punishment in the afterlife consists of reincarnation in an inferior realm?

– No

Notes: The punishment is beyond reincarnation in the inferior realm.

↳ Other form of punishment

–Specify: Painful burning in the hellfire.

↳ Supernatural punishments are meted out in this lifetime?

– No

Notes: Supernatural punishment is done in the afterlife.

Do supernatural beings bestow rewards in the text?

– No

Notes: The reward is only bestowed by God (Allah).

Messianism/Eschatology

Are messianic beliefs present in the text?

– No

Notes: The text did not mention messianic beliefs.

Is an eschatology present in the text?

– Yes

Notes: The text mentioned belief in some eschatological principles.

↳ Eschaton is in this lifetime

– No

Notes: Eschaton is in the afterlife.

↳ At specified time in future

– No

Notes: The time is not known to any except Allah.

↳ At unspecified time in near future

– No

Notes: The actual time is not known.

↳ At unspecified time in distant future

– No

Notes: The time remains secret to Allah alone.

↳ At some other time [specify]

– Yes

Notes: The time will be in the afterlife.

↳ Adherents need to perform specific tasks to bring about World's end

– No

Notes: Adherents do not influence the end of the world.

↳ Divine judgment event

– Yes

Notes: Divine judgment is to happen in the eschaton event.

↳ Restoration of the world

– No

Notes: A new world is to replace the existing one.

↳ Start of a new temporal cycle

– No

Notes: The eschaton marked the beginning of eternal life.

- ↳ Establishment of new political system
 - No
 - Notes: The entire system belongs to Allah (the creator of all).

- ↳ Establishment of new religious system
 - No
 - Notes: Religion is over by the end of the world.

- ↳ Other form of eschatology?
 - Specify: Paradise, Hellfire, etc.

- ↳ Will anyone survive the eschaton?
 - No
 - Notes: None survive the eschaton except God.

Norms & Moral Realism

Are general social norms prescribed by the text?

– Yes

Notes: The text prescribed some social norms in the first three pages.

Is there a conventional vs. moral distinction in the religious text?

– No

Notes: The text analyzed the only norms approved by Islam.

Are there centrally important virtues advocated by the text?

– Yes

Notes: The text advocated some norms and values that are vital in daily life.

↳ Honesty/trustworthiness/integrity

– Yes

Notes: The text recommended honesty.

↳ Courage (in battle)

– Yes

Notes: The text recommended courage.

↳ Courage (generic)

– Yes

Notes: The text instructed courage generally.

↳ Compassion/empathy/kindness/benevolence

– Yes

Notes: The text ordered Muslims towards kindness.

↳ Mercy/forgiveness/tolerance

– Yes

Notes: The text strongly advocated the habit of forgiveness.

↳ Generosity/charity

– Yes

Notes: The text urged believers to give out charity.

↳ Selflessness/selfless giving

– Yes

Notes: The text prohibited the habit of selfishness.

↳ Righteousness/moral rectitude

– Yes

Notes: The text directed Muslims to be righteous in all their dealings.

↳ Ritual purity/ritual adherence/abstention from sources of impurity

– Yes

Notes: The text separated subtopics for ritual purity.

↳ Respectfulness/courtesy

– Yes

Notes: The text directed Muslims on respectfulness to others.

↳ Familial obedience/filial piety

– Yes

Notes: The text advocated piety in all affairs.

↳ Fidelity/loyalty

– Yes

Notes: The text required Muslims to remain loyal to the directives of Shari'ah.

- ↳ Cooperation
 - Yes
 - Notes: The text advocated unity and cooperation among Muslims.
- ↳ Independence/creativity/freedom
 - Yes
 - Notes: The text recommends Muslims to be creative in life.
- ↳ Moderation/frugality
 - Yes
 - Notes: The text called for frugality.
- ↳ Forbearance/fortitude/patience
 - Yes
 - Notes: The text recommends bits of patience.
- ↳ Diligence/self-discipline/excellence
 - Yes
 - Notes: The text ordered Muslims to self-discipline.
- ↳ Assertiveness/decisiveness/confidence/initiative
 - Yes
 - Notes: The text guides to assertiveness.
- ↳ Strength (physical)
 - Yes
 - Notes: The text recommends strength to believers.
- ↳ Power/status/nobility
 - Yes
 - Notes: The text recommends Muslims not remain weak.
- ↳ Humility/modesty
 - Yes
 - Notes: The text called for modesty in life.
- ↳ Contentment/serenity/equanimity
 - Yes

Notes: The text prohibits greediness.

↳ Joyfulness/enthusiasm/cheerfulness

– Yes

Notes: The text recommends Muslims to be enthusiastic in life.

↳ Optimism/hope

– Yes

Notes: The text directed Muslims to set hope in Alla's assistance.

↳ Gratitude/thankfulness

– Yes

Notes: The text ordered gratitude behavior.

↳ Reverence/awe/wonder

– Yes

Notes: The text called for reverence.

↳ Faith/belief/trust/devotion

– Yes

Notes: The text ordered Muslims to set trust in Allah.

↳ Wisdom/understanding

– Yes

Notes: The text ordered Muslims to pursue wisdom wherever they found it.

↳ Discernment/intelligence

– Yes

Notes: The text recommended intelligence.

↳ Beauty/attractiveness

– Yes

Notes: The text recommends cleanliness to have beauty.

↳ Cleanliness (physical)/orderliness

– Yes

Notes: The text ordered Muslims to cleanliness.

↳ Other important virtues

– Yes

Notes: The text ordered devotion in worship.

Advocacy of Practices

Does the text require celibacy (full sexual abstinence)?

– No

Notes: The text forbids celibacy for people who have a legal spouse.

Does the text require constraints on sexual activity (partial sexual abstinence)?

– No

Notes: The text did not restrict lawful sexual activities.

Does the text require castration?

– No

Notes: The text prohibits castration.

Does the text require fasting?

– Yes

Notes: The text directed Muslims to fast in the month of Ramadan.

Does the text require forgone food opportunities (taboos on desired foods)?

– No

Notes: The text did not require forgone food opportunities.

Does the text require permanent scarring or painful bodily alterations?

– No

Notes: The text does not require permanent scarring.

Does the text require painful physical positions or transitory painful wounds?

– No

Notes: The text did not require a painful wound.

Does the text require sacrifice of adults?

– No

Notes: The text prohibits the sacrifice of adults.

Does the text require sacrifice of children?

– No

Notes: The text prohibits the sacrifice of children.

Does the text require self-sacrifice (suicide)?

– No

Notes: The text does not require suicide.

Does the text require sacrifice of property/valuable items?

– Yes

Notes: The text recommends the sacrifice of properties for charity.

Does the text require sacrifice of time (e.g. attendance at meetings or services, regular prayer, etc.)?

– Yes

Notes: The text directed for the sacrifice of time to attend a congregation of the five daily prayers.

Does the text require physical risk taking?

– No

Notes: The text did not require risk-taking that might lead to the loss of life without due cause.

Does the text require accepting ethical precepts?

– Yes

Notes: The text requires acceptance of ethical precepts that fulfilled the directives of Islam.

Does the text require marginalization by out-group members?

– No

Notes: The text called for unity.

Does the text require participation in small-scale rituals (private, household)?

– Yes

Notes: The text requires the attendance of prayer services.

What is the average interval of time between performances?

– Hours: 2

Does the text require participation in large-scale rituals?

– Yes

Notes: The text requires attendance of large-scale rituals on Friday and Eid occasions.

↳ On average, how many participants gather in one location?

– Number of participants: 1000

Notes: The number begins from twelve people to unlimited.

↳ Interval of time between performances (in hours)

– Hours: 168

Notes: For the performance of the weekly Friday prayer.

↳ Are there orthodoxy checks?

– Yes

↳ Are there orthopraxy checks?

– No

↳ Does participation entail synchronic practices?

– Yes

Notes: The rituals are stipulated for a particular period.

↳ Is there use of intoxicants?

– No

Notes: The text prohibits the use of intoxicants.

Are extra-ritual in-group markers present as indicated in the text?

– No

Notes: The text does not require grouping in the extra ritual activities.

Does the text employ fictive kinship terminology?

– No

Notes: The text rejects fictive terminology.

Does the text include elements that are intended to be entertaining?

– No

Notes: The text did not employ entertainment elements.

Does the text specify sacrifices, offerings, and maintenance of a sacred space?

– Yes

Notes: The text requires the sacrifice of animals on Eid Day.

↳ Are sacrifices specified by the text?

– Yes

↳ Animal sacrifice?

– Yes

Notes: The text is directed toward the sacrifice of animals on Eid day.

↳ Human sacrifice?

– No

Notes: The text prohibits the sacrifice of humans.

↳ Are there self-sacrifices specified by the text?

– No

Notes: The text does not require self-sacrifice.

↳ Are there material offerings present?

– Yes

Notes: The text called for material offerings.

↳ Are they mandatory?

– Yes

Notes: The text directed material offerings in the form of obligatory charity (Zakat) on those having the due amount of the charity.

↳ Are they composed of valuable objects?

– Yes

Notes: They compose money, precious stones, animals, and crops.

↳ Are they composed of daily-life objects?

– Yes

Notes: Especially crops and animals.

↳ Are material offerings interred at this place (in caches)?

– No

Notes: The materials are given to poor people.

↳ Are there particular smells associated with material offerings?

– No

Notes: No smell is required on the materials.

↳ Are there particular visual stimuli (colors, symbols) associated with the offerings? (I.e. 'must be bright' 'must include red')

– No

Notes: The materials must be valuable alone.

↳ Other?

–Specify: The materials must not have defects.

↳ Is attendance to worship/sacrifice mandatory?

– No

Notes: Attendance of sacrifice is not mandatory.

↳ Is the maintenance of the place regulated by the text?

– Yes

Notes: The text recommended maintainance of the places of worships.

↳ Is it required?

– Yes

Notes: Maintainance of the place is required.

↳ Is there cleansing (for the maintenance)?

– Yes

Notes: The text orders the cleaning of the mosques.

↳ Are there periodic repairs/reconstructions?

– No

Notes: The text did not specify the time of maintenance to the place.

↳ Is the maintenance performed by permanent staff?

– No

Notes: Maintenance is voluntary.

↳ Other?

–Specify: All sorts of dirt must be kept away from the place.

Institutions & Production Environment of Text

Is bureaucracy regulated by this text?

– Yes

Notes: The text limits attention to the interaction of adherents with the bureaucrats on matters that did not go contrary to the directives of Islamic law (Shari'ah).

↳ Does the text regulate bureaucracy permanently?

– Yes

Notes: Bureaucracy is subjected to obedience to the divine law of the creator (Allah).

↳ Does the text regulate bureaucracy temporarily/seasonally?

– No

Notes: The text regulated bureaucracy permanently towards obedience to the directives of the divine law.

↳ Does the text dictate how the group's adherent's interact with a formal bureaucracy within their group?

– Yes

Notes: Adherents are restricted from obedience to the directives of bureaucrats when they go contrary to the orders of the creator (Allah).

↳ Does the text dictate how individuals interact with other institutional bureaucracies?

– Yes

Notes: All interaction with other institutional bureaucracy shall not exceed the limit of the divine law (Shari'ah).

↳ Does the text regulate the primary supporting income of the place?

– Yes

Notes: The text directed that all usable income shall come from lawful sources.

↳ Does the text provide for provisions to lease out land?

– No

Notes: The text did not extend discussion on the lease of land.

↳ Does the text provide for provisions to lease out tools?

– No

Notes: The text did not analyze the principles of leasing land.

Does the text mention warfare?

– No

Notes: The text did not mention warfare.

Society of religious group that produced the text is best characterized as:

– An empire

Notes: Most societies to have applied the text are empires, such as the Songhai Empire.

Does the text specify forms of taxation?

– No

Notes: The text did not guide tax collection.

Does the text detail interaction with public works?

– Yes

Notes: The text made highlight the interaction with public works.

↳ Does the text advocate for public food storage?

– No

Notes: The text did not guide the principles of public food storage.

↳ Does the text provide guidance for food distribution?

– No

Notes: The text did not discuss food storage.

↳ Does the text regulate places for civic functions?

– Yes

Notes: The text directed the application of integrity while relating to others.

↳ Does the text regulate places for the practice of justice?

– Yes

Notes: The text called for justice when judging between two quarreling parties.

↳ Does the text advocate or specify controls for water management (irrigation, flood control)?

– No

Notes: The text regulated the management of water during ablution or ritual baths.

↳ Does the text specify restrictions on common transportation?

– No

Notes: The text remained an introductory book that did not extend discussion on the transportation system in Islamic jurisprudence.

↳ Other form of regulation of public works?

–Specify: The text was highly restricted to worship alone.

Does the text mentioned food production/disbursement?

– No

Notes: The text did not make a discussion on food disbursement.

Are there formal educational institutions available for teaching the text?

– Yes

Notes: The text was set among the syllabus of the formal Islamic schools in the region.

Does the text specify institutionalized famine relief?

– No

Notes: The text restricted discussion on the Islamic system of worship (Ibadat).

Does the text specify institutionalized poverty relief?

– No

Notes: The text had not extended to the poverty relief mechanism.

Are there specific elements of society that have controlled the reproduction of the text?

– An empire

Are there formal educational institutions specified according to the text?

– Yes

Notes: The text indicated approval to only schools teaching religious education.

Are there specific elements of society involved with the destruction of the text?

– Other

Notes: No Islamic society is associated with the destruction of the text.

Does the text specify institutionalized care for elderly & infirm?

– No

Notes: The text was made of worship alone.

Does the text make provisions for non-religious education?

– No

Notes: The text concentrated on religious education alone.

Does the text restrict education to religious professionals?

– No

Notes: The text had not restricted education to religious professionals alone but directed its search to the entire public.

Other forms of welfare?

– No

Notes: The text remained silent on the welfare system.

Does the text restrict education among religious professionals?

– No

Notes: Education is left open to the entire people.

Is education gendered according to the text?

– No

Notes: Education is meant for both the male and female sexes.

Is education gendered with respect to this text and larger textual tradition?

– No

Notes: Education is not restricted to any particular gender.

Does the text specify teaching relationships or ratios? (i.e.: 1:20; 1:1)

– No

Notes: The text did not specify the teaching relationship.

Are there specific relationships to teachers that are advocated by the text?

– No

Notes: The text did not advocated any relationship to teacher.

Are there worldly rewards/benefits to education according to the text specified by the text itself?

– No

Notes: The text did not mentioned any worldly benefit to the education.

Society & Institutions

Society of religious group that produced the text is best characterized as:

– An empire

Notes: Most societies to have applied the text are empires, such as the Songhai Empire.

Are there specific elements of society that have controlled the reproduction of the text?

– An empire

Are there specific elements of society involved with the destruction of the text?

– Other

Notes: No Islamic society is associated with the destruction of the text.

Welfare

Does the text specify institutionalized famine relief?

– No

Notes: The text restricted discussion on the Islamic system of worship (Ibadat).

Does the text specify institutionalized poverty relief?

– No

Notes: The text had not extended to the poverty relief mechanism.

Does the text specify institutionalized care for elderly & infirm?

– No

Notes: The text was made of worship alone.

Other forms of welfare?

– No

Notes: The text remained silent on the welfare system.

Education

Are there formal educational institutions available for teaching the text?

– Yes

Notes: The text was set among the syllabus of the formal Islamic schools in the region.

Are there formal educational institutions specified according to the text?

– Yes

Notes: The text indicated approval to only schools teaching religious education.

Does the text make provisions for non-religious education?

– No

Notes: The text concentrated on religious education alone.

Does the text restrict education to religious professionals?

– No

Notes: The text had not restricted education to religious professionals alone but directed its search to the entire public.

Does the text restrict education among religious professionals?

– No

Notes: Education is left open to the entire people.

Is education gendered according to the text?

– No

Notes: Education is meant for both the male and female sexes.

Is education gendered with respect to this text and larger textual tradition?

– No

Notes: Education is not restricted to any particular gender.

Does the text specify teaching relationships or ratios? (i.e.: 1:20; 1:1)

– No

Notes: The text did not specify the teaching relationship.

Are there specific relationships to teachers that are advocated by the text?

– No

Notes: The text did not advocated any relationship to teacher.

Are there worldly rewards/benefits to education according to the text specified by the text itself?

– No

Notes: The text did not mentioned any worldly benefit to the education.

Bureaucracy

Is bureaucracy regulated by this text?

– Yes

Notes: The text limits attention to the interaction of adherents with the bureaucrats on matters that did not go contrary to the directives of Islamic law (Shari'ah).

Does the text regulate bureaucracy permanently?

– Yes

Notes: Bureaucracy is subjected to obedience to the divine law of the creator (Allah).

Does the text regulate bureaucracy temporarily/seasonally?

– No

Notes: The text regulated bureaucracy permanently towards obedience to the directives of the

divine law.

↳ Does the text dictate how the group's adherents interact with a formal bureaucracy within their group?

– Yes

Notes: Adherents are restricted from obedience to the directives of bureaucrats when they go contrary to the orders of the creator (Allah).

↳ Does the text dictate how individuals interact with other institutional bureaucracies?

– Yes

Notes: All interaction with other institutional bureaucracy shall not exceed the limit of the divine law (Shari'ah).

↳ Does the text regulate the primary supporting income of the place?

– Yes

Notes: The text directed that all usable income shall come from lawful sources.

↳ Does the text provide for provisions to lease out land?

– No

Notes: The text did not extend discussion on the lease of land.

↳ Does the text provide for provisions to lease out tools?

– No

Notes: The text did not analyze the principles of leasing land.

Public Works

Does the text detail interaction with public works?

– Yes

Notes: The text made highlight the interaction with public works.

↳ Does the text advocate for public food storage?

– No

Notes: The text did not guide the principles of public food storage.

↳ Does the text provide guidance for food distribution?

– No

Notes: The text did not discuss food storage.

↳ Does the text regulate places for civic functions?

– Yes

Notes: The text directed the application of integrity while relating to others.

↳ Does the text regulate places for the practice of justice?

– Yes

Notes: The text called for justice when judging between two quarreling parties.

↳ Does the text advocate or specify controls for water management (irrigation, flood control)?

– No

Notes: The text regulated the management of water during ablution or ritual baths.

↳ Does the text specify restrictions on common transportation?

– No

Notes: The text remained an introductory book that did not extend discussion on the transportation system in Islamic jurisprudence.

↳ Other form of regulation of public works?

– Specify: The text was highly restricted to worship alone.

Taxation

Does the text specify forms of taxation?

– No

Notes: The text did not guide tax collection.

Warfare

Does the text mention warfare?

– No

Notes: The text did not mention warfare.

Food Production

Does the text mentioned food production/disbursement?

– No

Notes: The text did not make a discussion on food disbursement.

Bibliography

General References

Reference: (A brief introduction to the Islamic jurisprudence on the Maliki school of law) مختصر الأخصري في مذهب الإمام مالك, ash-Shafi'i ibn Idriss, Muhammad. Al-shafi'i's Risala: Treatise on the Foundations of Islamic Jurisprudence. Translated by Mahid Khadduri. Vol. 1. UK: Islamic Texts Society, 1987.

Reference: (A brief introduction to the Islamic jurisprudence on the Maliki school of law) مختصر الأخصري في مذهب الإمام مالك, Mughal, Munir Ahmad. "Islamic Jurisprudence", 2000. <https://doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.1903980>.